

**INNOVATION IN THE SERVICE SECTOR AS AN ECONOMIC
CATEGORY**

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The development of the service sector creates new demand for goods and services and a new competitive environment. Covering all sectors affected by innovation activity, the following main types of innovation activity can be distinguished:[1]

- market research;
- scientific research and development;
- software developments;
- technological preparation for production;
- education and training of personnel;
- reorganization of the enterprise management system;
- change business processes.[2]

At the current stage of economic development not only in the Republic of Uzbekistan, but also throughout the world, very little innovative activity is carried out in the field of software development and technological developments in the service sector, and ready-made developments developed by technical enterprises are mainly used.[3]. This implies that the innovative development of a single enterprise is not enough. The overall innovative development of an entire region is necessary[4]. Only then will it be possible to exchange the results of the innovative activities of enterprises in different sectors and mutually beneficial experiences with new models of organizational management[5].

The principles and directions of innovative development mentioned above can further expand the concept of innovation as an economic category. This serves

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to identify the main components of innovation that are useful in managing innovative development in service enterprises.[6].

Figure 1.5. Innovation as an economic category1

Having studied the economic content of innovation and analyzed the research on it, it can be said that innovation can be understood as a product of science, a measure aimed at innovation in a relevant field, a material result obtained from an investment aimed at organizing a new form of service provision and management, and a process that transforms the proposed idea into a finished product and service[7]. The main characteristics of innovation are the risks associated with its proposal and implementation, the uncertainty of the result of innovation and the demand for it, and the complexity required in this process, such as the need for strong knowledge and skills. The result of innovation is economic, social, environmental and multiplicative, depending on which area it is aimed at reforming[8].

LIST OF REFERENCES

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